

entropy ($\Delta S^\ddagger$) of activation in acetic acid-water medium are 80.7 kJ mol⁻¹, 88.6 kJ mol⁻¹ and -25.9 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ respectively. The enthalpy of activation ($\Delta H^\ddagger$) in aqueous medium is 76.1 kJ mol⁻¹. The enthalpy of activation in both the media is almost the same indicating that acetic acid is not involved in the transition state of the rate determining step.

The effect of concentration of manganic pyrophosphate, mandelic acid and pyrophosphate on rate of oxidation of mandelic acid suggests that there is a fast reversible formation of a complex between Mn(III) pyrophosphate and mandelic acid with the displacement of pyrophosphate ligand as follows (eq. 1).

The rate determining step is breaking of complex with C-C cleavage and free radical formation (eq. 2)

The free radical $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{---}\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}(\text{OH})$ again reacts with Mn(III) forming benzaldehyde as follows (eq. 3)

The above proposed scheme (eqs. 1 to 3) would lead to the following rate expression (4)

$$-\frac{d[\text{Mn(III)}]}{dt} = \frac{k [\text{Mandelic acid}] [\text{Mn(III)}]}{\left\{ \frac{[\text{Pyrophosphate}]}{K} + [\text{Mandelic acid}] \right\}} \quad \text{(4)}$$

The rate expression is quite consistent with the experimentally observed rate data. The decrease in the rate of oxidation due to increase in either acetic acid or dioxane concentration may be due to the effect of dielectric constant of the medium. The solvent effect suggests that the reaction may be of dipole-dipole type. Thus, the manganic pyrophosphate species involved in the reaction may be $[\text{Mn(III)}(\text{H}_3\text{P}_2\text{O}_7)_3]$ rather than $[\text{Mn(III)}(\text{H}_3\text{P}_3\text{O}_7)_3]^{3-}$ to account for the observed effect of solvent. The value of enthalpy of activation, 80.7 kJ mol⁻¹, corresponds to C-C bond fission and supports the formation of benzaldehyde as the product of oxidation.

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Synthesis and Biological Activities of Derivatives of Mercaptobenzimidazoles. Part-II : Some Reactions of 2-Mercapto-5 (or 6)-Nitro and 2-Mercapto-4 (or 7)-Nitrobenzimidazoles

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THE syntheses and biological activities of certain perhydrothiazino-, perhydrothiazolobenzimidazoles and thiazolo[3,2-a]-benzimidazole-3(2H)-ones and their benzylidene derivatives have been reported¹⁻⁷. As a part of our studies on substituted mercaptobenzimidazoles⁸, we report here some cyclization reactions of 2-mercapto-4 (or 7)-nitro and 2-mercapto-5 (or 6)-nitrobenzimidazoles (Scheme 1), and the biological activities of the products.

2-Mercapto-5 (or 6)-nitro and 2-mercapto-4 (or 7)-nitrobenzimidazoles (IIa, b) have been synthesized by adopting a standard procedure⁹, starting from 4-nitro-, and 3-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamines (Ia, b), respectively. The reaction of II with 1,2-dibromoethane resulted in the formation of a single product

Scheme 1

TABLE I—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF DERIVATIVES OF MERCAPTOBENZIMIDAZOLES

Compound	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	% Nitrogen*		IR data (cm ⁻¹)	PMR data (CDCl ₃) in δ ppm
				Found	(Calcd.)		
IIIa	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	175	68	18.89 (19.00)	18.92 (19.00)	1565 1610 (C-N)(C=N)	4.42 (t, 2H, S-CH ₂); 5.14 (t, 2H, N-CH ₂) and 7.28-7.50 (m, 3H, Ar).
IIIb	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	120	68	18.92 (19.00)	17.78 (17.87)	1560 1610 (C-N)(C=N)	4.89 (t, 2H, S-CH ₂); 5.12 (t, 2H, N-CH ₂) and 7.18-7.45 (m, 3H Ar).
Va	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	165	67	17.78 (17.87)	17.79 (17.87)	1570 1605 (C-N)(C=N)	—
Vb	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	145	61	17.79 (17.87)	16.53 (16.60)	1570 1610 (C-N)(C=N)	4.18 (t, 2H, N-CH ₂); 3.65 (t, 2H, S-CH ₂); 2.1 (q, 2H, -CH ₂ -) and 7.25-7.48 (m, 3H, Ar).
VIIa	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	190 (decomp)	74	16.53 (16.60)	16.71 (16.60)	1620 2265-2680 (C=N (CO ₂ H)) 3325-3380 (NH)	—
VIIb	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	240 (decomp)	76	16.71 (16.60)	17.80 (17.87)	1625 2370-2700 (C=N) (CO ₂ H) 3325-3385 (NH)	—
VIIIa	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	168	62	17.98 (17.87)	17.85 (17.87)	1740 (>N-C=O)	4.35 (s, 2H, S-CH ₂); 7.15-7.48 (m, 2H, Ar); and 7.89 (m, 1H, Ar C ₆ -H or C ₈ -H).
VIIIb	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	210	60	17.80 (17.87)	17.35 (17.35)	1735 (>N-C=O)	4.35 (s, 2H, S-CH ₂); 6.98-7.42 (m, 2H, Ar) and 7.80 (m, 1H, Ar C ₆ -H).
Xa	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	222-24	70	12.88 (13.00)	12.91 (13.00)	1730 (>N-C=O)	6.10 (s, 1H, =CH); 7.0-7.42 (m, 7H, Ar) and 7.82 (m, 1H, Ar C ₆ -H or C ₈ -H).
Xb	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	218-19	65	12.91 (13.00)	12.91 (13.00)	1730 (>N-C=O)	6.10 (s, 1H, =CH); 6.98-7.40 (m, 7H, Ar) and 7.84 (m, 1H, Ar C ₆ -H).

* Analyses for C and H were also found satisfactory.

(tlc), the corresponding nitro-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[3,2-a]-benzimidazole (III or IV). The ir spectrum of this product showed the absence of -NH and -SH absorption frequencies indicating cyclization.

A similar reaction of II with 1,3-bromochloropropane resulted in the formation of a single, but corresponding nitro-2,3-dihydro-4H-1,3-thiazino[3,2-a]-benzimidazole (V or VI).

2-Mercaptobenzimidazoles (II) have been reacted with chloroacetic acid in presence of a base to get the corresponding nitro-2-benzimidazolylthioacetic acids (VII), which on heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine undergo cyclization, again yielding a single product in each case (tlc), the corresponding thiazolo[3,2-a]-benzimidazol-3(2H)-one (VIII or IX).

The cyclized compound from VIIb may have either structure VIIIb or IXb. If structure IXb is correct, there should not be any deshielding effect of thiazolidinone ring on C_5-H . But the pmr spectrum of cyclized product of VIIb showed a signal at δ 7.87, indicating greater deshielding at C_5-H . This deshielding effect on C_5 periproton is due to the magnetic anisotropy of carbonyl group with some contribution from the rest of the ring. This decides in favour of VIIIb. This observation is in agreement with a recent report of Jain and Pujari¹⁰. In the case of cyclized product of VIIa, two protons at C_6 and C_8 are in similar environments as they are adjacent to a nitro group and therefore resonate closely. A deshielded proton in its pmr spectrum indicates again a C_6 periproton and formation of an angular isomer VIIIa as in the earlier case.

On the basis of this, structures III and IV have been assigned to thiazolobenzimidazoles and thiazinobenzimidazoles, respectively. This observation is also in agreement with the fact that 4 (or 7)-nitro-, and 5 (or 6)-nitrobenzimidazoles react by S_E2' mechanism probably through their 1,7- and 1,6-tautomers, respectively^{11,12}.

Compounds VIIIa, b on condensation with benzaldehyde in presence of sodium acetate yielded their 2-benzylidene derivatives (Xa, b).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Physical, analytical and spectral data are presented in Table 1.

Nitro-thiazolo[3,2-a]-benzimidazol-3(2H)-ones (III) and nitro-2,3-dihydro-4H-1,3-thiazino[3,2-a]-benzimidazoles (V): A mixture of II (0.005 mole) and 1,2-dibromoethane or 1,3-bromochloropropane (0.005 mole) in isopropanol and sodium bicarbonate (13.6 g) was stirred with 20% aq. KOH, for 1 hr, then refluxed for 3 hr. Isopropanol was removed, the residue cooled and treated with aq. KOH. It was extracted with chloroform and compound III or V was obtained on removal of solvent.

Nitro-2-benzimidazolyl-thioacetic acids (VII): A mixture of compound II (0.1 mole) and chloroacetic acid (0.1 mole) in 10% aq. NaOH (80 ml) was heated for 2 hr on a steam bath. The reaction mixture was cooled and acidified to get VII.

Nitro-thiazolo[3,2-a]-benzimidazol-3(2H)-ones (VIII): A mixture of VII (10 g), pyridine (3 ml) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) was heated on a steam bath for 1.5 hr and cooled. The solid obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallized from alcohol to yield VIII.

Nitro-2-benzylidene-thiazolo[3,2-a]-benzimidazol-3(2H)-ones (X): A mixture of VIII (2.1 g), benzaldehyde (1.1 g) and sodium acetate (1.0 g) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr and cooled. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with cold water and dried to get X, which was recrystallized from alcohol.

Biological activities:

Antimicrobial activity: The compounds synthesized have been evaluated for their antibacterial activity by standard methods¹³ against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Sarcina lutea*. The fungi used for evaluation of antifungal activity were *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Trychophyton mentagrophytes*. The compounds exhibited moderate to strong antifungal activity but a weak antibacterial activity.

Anthelmintic activity: The compounds were also screened for their anthelmintic property adopting a standard procedure¹⁴ and using piperazine citrate as the standard. The compounds (Xa, b) showed to be more potential anthelmintic agents; the rest being moderate.

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